

An Individual Multidisciplinary Profile based on the Science Map. Macro- to micro- Approaches

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Abstract

Maps of science can serve not only as a multi-modal interface to study the development of scientific fields, but also as a base platform for analysing the disciplinary interests of individual scientists. In the first case, these are macro- and meso-scale studies and there are plenty of software tools dedicated to such tasks – e.g., InCite or SciVal that use the two largest global scholar databases. However, there are few tools for analysing scientific activity at the micro level – i.e., the individual researcher, drawn from local databases, which are often the most representative for a given institution. The authors present such an interface for multidimensional analyses of individual scientific development. They pay particular attention to the definition of the multidisciplinary factor, which they calculate using the topological specificity of the nationwide journal map. Moreover, the authors evaluate it using another both database and metadata.

Introduction

The development of a research field or an individual's interest is increasingly being studied, especially as it relates to innovation in science (Wang & Barabási, 2021). Such studies are likely to give insight into how major findings develop, hopefully also leading to more of them. This is especially important in relation to the development and use of technology in science, which is not only being adopted to help in the analysis of data but creating entirely new areas of study. One area that is of particular interest in terms of technology is the ability to more easily track development over time, using e.g., bibliometric data and research interest classifications. Such a tool could be able to characterize the theoretical effectiveness of achieving research success dependent on the design of the team. Methods applied thus far, using classical divisions for interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary research, do not appear to be effective enough; in particular, when research teams are created combining different areas of knowledge (Abramo, D'Angelo & Zhang, 2022). It is also becoming necessary to define new parameters to dynamically identify domain characteristics for individual researchers. In addition, it appears indispensable to revise some research activities in the new definition of scientific fields.

A good example, pointing to the problems in question, is biophysics, which is a novel field, which has recently made its transition from an interdisciplinary outpost to its own field. Today, biophysics is treated as a research area that has already created its own research paradigm, rather than simply drawing on the achievements of its 'parents': biology and physics (Banks, 2022). Similar problems apply to other research areas, where only two scientific disciplines come together. While it is true that often the two core disciplines try to claim dominance within the new field, the best option seems to be to recognize it as a separate field of study. An important task, therefore, is to come up with new solutions that will be useful for individual

researchers and identify new areas of research that combine basic scientific disciplines defined in different countries, according to the legislation on the development of science.

This raises the very important issue of creating an effective expert tool that will be able to characterise the theoretical effectiveness of achieving research success dependent on the contribution of a particular researcher. While most visualization software is dedicated to macro analyses, individual user exploration needs remain disregarded. To redress this lack, the authors first considered the individual researchers' activity, in many overlapping contexts. Micro studies require reference to the distribution of scientometric data on a macro level, thus the authors start from presenting a landscape derived from the arrangement of scientific journals based on the disciplinary classification system in Poland.

Review of literature on multidisciplinary research

The paradigm of multidisciplinary research includes three concepts: multi-, inter- and transdisciplinarity. They all stem from the interaction between disciplines depending on the issue addressed. Multidisciplinarity involves studying a research topic not just in one discipline, but in several at the same time, while remaining within their boundaries (Nicolescu, 2014). Interdisciplinarity is most often concerned with the transfer of methods from one discipline to another, synthesising the links between them. Transdisciplinarity is a variant of interdisciplinarity, in which boundaries between and beyond disciplines are crossed and knowledge and perspectives from different scientific disciplines, as well as non-scientific sources, are integrated (National Academy of Sciences, 2004; Choi & Pak, 2006). Contemporary science researchers are most often interested in interdisciplinarity, which has developed as a result of the evolution of research technologies that usually came from other fields of knowledge. Today, we are witnessing a very dynamic growth in the importance of digital technologies in the analysis, presentation, and prediction of the scope of scientific research (Altmejd et al., 2019).

In scientometrics, it has become acceptable to use maps of science in the study of interactions between disciplines. The maps of science serve as a substrate, a base layer for visual representation reproducing the structure of research topics communicated in the collection of articles, most often from the WoS (Soós, Vida & Schubert, 2018). By visualising citation networks in relation to WoS subject categories, it is possible to explore thematic variation in a range of aspects. This framework has been called science overlay mapping (Rafols, Porter & Leydesdorff, 2010). The study of interdisciplinarity implies the creation of special metrics (indicators) in quantitative research. To distinguish the development of different research fields and determine the boundaries between them, a cluster analysis of scientometric data is usually carried out concerning such characteristics as abundance, balance or concentration and diversity (Soós, Vida & Schubert, 2018). The boundaries between domains (clusters) are usually poorly defined and blurred. In their determination, models using Shannon entropy and network analysis with centrality measures are used (Leydesdorff, Rafols & Chen, 2013).

The overlay framework was applied in examining the degree and patterns of interdisciplinarity in relation to selected disciplines and research field issues. This approach enables the analysis of the intensity of cooperation between different institutions. The patterns of collaboration, read from visualizations, are analyzed and contrasted with those of research in classical disciplines. The subject of interdisciplinarity may be selected issues and fields of research, e.g., nanotechnology (Schummer, 2004), or a particular number of disciplines (Porter & Rafols, 2009). Specifically, the frameworks and boundaries of social sciences and humanities are systematically discussed (Soós, Vida & Schubert, 2018).

As some researchers point out, while in studies of interdisciplinarity, work focuses on the search for objective quantitative measures, “measuring” multidisciplinary comes more easily (Calver, Bryant & Wardell-Johnson, 2018; Mennes, 2020). Evaluation is then possible through the classification of journals, e.g., subject categories of WoS, in which the articles of the analysed set of articles are counted. In addition to the quantitative view of multidisciplinary, traditionally embodied in citations and a number of publications, some scientometricians evaluate its second dimension – research excellence (Wagner et al., 2011).

Multidisciplinary is often referred to in the context of teams formed by people with different, often very distant, specialities. The key problem then is to acquire data on the specialisation or scientific focus of individuals. Such information can be provided by academic networking platforms such as ResearchGate or Academia.edu or local university bibliographic databases. Data on individual scientific interests can be used in multidisciplinary models, such as the T-shape (Turner et al. 2019). This model is inspired by human knowledge, both deep, specialised (the stem of the letter T) and wide, extensive, multidisciplinary (the crossbeam of the letter T). On a similar basis, the degree and extent of cooperation in multidisciplinary institutions is explored (Zuo & Zhao, 2018).

The idea that multidisciplinary can be “traced” through two channels, i.e., individual interests and publishing patterns, was used in this study. The authors did not need to set boundaries between disciplines – their concept combines areas of scientific interest and determines their geometry using topological methods (Osińska, 2019). A disciplinary map of journals, representative of the whole country, was used as the basic layout.

Map of Polish Science – the macro approach

The choice of the journal to which we send the manuscript is determined by the subject of the text. To facilitate this choice for authors and, more recently, for expert systems based on artificial intelligence, the editors describe the journal’s thematic scope by reference to a list of selected scientific disciplines. This list may include one or two disciplinary categories, or as many as ten, as some Polish scientific editors have done. (Kulczycki, 2017). To meet the challenge of systematising access to scientific literature, the Polish Ministry of Science has created a standardized *New Extended List of Scientific Journals and Peer-reviewed Materials from International Conferences*, which it updates regularly (3rd ed., 2021). As of the third quarter of 2022, the list contains 32,701 journals, the vast majority of these being international. The number of disciplines to which journals on the list are assigned is 45. This follows from the current Classification of Science in Poland established in 2018 (*List of areas of academic study...*, 2018). They are grouped into eight main domain areas: natural and exact sciences, engineering and technology, medical and health sciences, social sciences, agricultural sciences, the humanities, theological sciences, and the arts. Table 1 shows the number and percentage of journals assigned to disciplines. The 32701×45 matrix was visualized using a directed graph with a *force-directed layout* (Jacomy et al. 2014).

Table 1. Co-discipline distribution on the Ministerial journals’ list.

<i>Codiscipline number</i>	<i>Number of journals</i>	<i>Percentage ratio (%)</i>
1	5461	16.7
2	5755	17.6
3	6246	19.1
4	5265	16.1

5	3761	11.5
≥ 6	6213	19.0

The resulting map in Fig. 1 shows the disciplines – coloured nodes – and their associated journals from the ministerial list as scattered black dots or dots organised into separate clusters. The map shows the local grouping of disciplines and their logical distribution in relation to their nearest neighbours. The humanities (blue circles) are positioned next to the social disciplines (grey circles) – this proximity is explained by taxonomic and methodological closeness between social sciences and the humanities (SSH). On the other side of the graph, the natural sciences (aqua color) overlay technical sciences (magenta). Medical sciences, on the other hand, are at the edge of the network, but close to technical sciences, indicating the use of IT methods and tools. An interesting feature here is psychology, classified as a social discipline whose node is attracted by medical sciences. This situation is reflected in researcher discussions about the place of psychology in medicine (Castelnuovo, 2010). Agricultural sciences (green circles) are also isolated, surrounding the nodes of biological sciences. The semantic proximity of biology and veterinary science should not come as a surprise. Theology, associated throughout the world with the humanities and placed within these disciplines, has been given a separate category in Poland because it focuses not on man, but God (yellow color). The arts are most often interpreted in conjunction with the humanities, confirming their positioning within the field of humanities.

Figure 1. A disciplinary map of scientific journals from the Ministerial list. The coloured circles represent disciplines grouped into 8 main domains.

There are a number of algorithms for mapping science described in the scientometrics literature (Börner, Chen & Boyack, 2003; Chen, 2017). An issue on which map science researchers are currently particularly focused on is the evaluation of mapping algorithms (Waltman, Boyack & Colavizza et al., 2019). One of the evaluation measures is the domain clustering quality measure Q , which calculates the local – global diversity relationship on the map (Osinska, 2020). For the map presented in Fig. 1, calculated on the basis of the proportion of “foreign” domains in the clusters, the clustering quality Q reaches up to 0.804, while for the t -SNE algorithm (van der Maaten & Hinton, 2008), increasingly used in scientometric research, it is 0.312. This variation explains why a map generated using a force directed algorithm was chosen for further work. For comparison: by 2018, 171 disciplines were used to map Polish-language journals in over 4,500 sources. The co-occurrence of disciplines in this set corresponded to exponential distribution, making the t -SNE algorithm very suitable for mapping journals (Osinska, 2020). *Web of Science Subject Classification for All Databases* (2012) are currently grouped into only three subject categories: 1) the arts and humanities, 2) science and technology, and 3) social sciences. If such a minimalist division were to be applied to the distribution of disciplines on the map in Fig. 1, we would obtain a complete disjunction of the three classes (the group of medical sciences - red circles, is not taken into account as it is a separate classification). Dedicated for medicine and healthcare literature are the Medline database and the Pubmed searching tool. Therefore, the choice of basic domain areas and their number remain a contentious issue.

The Scientific Visualizer Application: action and functions – a micro approach

In terms of scientometric data visualization, tools and data sets geared towards macro and meso analyses dominate. Scientometrists are particularly interested in processes taking place in global or country-level science. In contrast, much less attention is paid to the development of tools dedicated to the study of science at an individual level. To address these shortcomings, the authors designed a web application, Scientific Visualizer, dedicated to micro, i.e., the individual analysis of researchers’ output in multiple overlapping contexts.

Data

A Nicolaus Copernicus University (NCU) bibliographic database called Expertus was used as the data set. This software, produced by Splendor, is first and foremost a dedicated software solution to manage information about working papers and published research and, in such a way, is widely used in Polish libraries and information centers of universities and research institutes (*Splendor® Information*, 2019). This is an information platform used by most Polish universities, so the application can potentially be used in other centers in Poland. Expertus uses the Dublin Core standard for object description, as well as filtering and searching tasks. A single record contains 30 subfields. Apart from standard bibliographic metadata describing entities: authors (name, affiliation), publication (title, year, language, abstract and keywords), journal (title, IF) and publisher (name, open access policy), the record notes how many points the Ministry of Education and Science has awarded to a journal, which is currently the most important indicator of the journal’s prestige. The disciplines and science domains ascribed to journals, according to the Polish classification of science, are also listed. It is worth emphasizing that for NCU researchers, Expertus is the most complete source of bibliographic data. Each researcher can generate a file in various formats containing all his/her bibliographic records. This unit file was used as input for the Scientific Visualiser.

To parse data, we used the rtf-parser library (parser), custom string operations and regular expressions to retrieve desired information and build an array of record objects used for all visualizations. The array of publication data is stored in-memory for visualizing. All

information, which needs to be stored at the server side, was saved using a NoSQL document database – MongoDB. The application is based on the web framework Express, which allows the user to render templates and create all required endpoints for retrieving data or for routing between application components. For the manipulation of geocoding data in map visualization, we used an open-source leaflet library (Leaflet).

Application

The web application was developed using the JavaScript programming language in a NodeJS environment. An express framework served as a skeleton of an entire app rendering layouts, routing between them, managing sessions, translating, and creating HTTP endpoints, which served to retrieve data from the server. Most of the visualization scripts, which use a D3.js library, run in the browser, using data from the files uploaded by the user without the need to fetch any data from the server. Visualizations based on the D3.js library are interactive: the scholars receive additional information about metadata in pop-up fields; they can also filter data by setting a threshold value in the appropriate panel. Finally, they can download each visualization layout as a PDF file. The source code is published in a public repository under the following address <https://gitlab.com/hotone/vis>. Ultimately, the application will be placed on the university's website visualizeme.umk.pl.

The application is protected with a password for data security and archiving purposes. The user has to first download an RTF file containing bibliographic records from the Expertus database. Scientific Visualizer (SV) allows individual analyses to be carried out in all possible contexts used in modern scientometrics (Börner, 2015). Primarily, temporal analysis shows how the scholar's publishing habits changed over time on a stacked bar chart (button 1 in Fig. 2). It allows scholars to compare the different forms of published units, such as: articles, books, and conference papers. The graph provides collaboration analysis, which is an important part of planning future scientific research at a global and international level (button 2 in Fig. 2). We can also access the information about the place (city and occasionally country) where the books and papers were published and perform geospatial analysis provided by button 3. At this stage, the coordinates (longitude and latitude) of cities are established through searching city names in a static JSON file. A bubble chart (button 5) presents those indicators most important for Polish academics, as they constitute the basis for their professional advancement. Researchers can see how the yearly ministerial scores change over years.

Figure 2. A screenshot of the Scientific Visualizer interface (buttons 1-6 provide different types of analysis).

Every scholar is interested in a general view of their scientific output in relation to the traditions of their discipline. Only metadata, such as keywords and disciplinary classification, provide qualitative information, i.e., verified by experts, regarding the scholar's area of research. We used these metadata to conduct topical analysis and create two semantic spaces relating to our own research. The first one consists of a keywords cloud, i.e., displays how frequently a given keyword appears in a given body of text – the frequency is reflected by the size of a given word (button 6). The second visualisation of the space of scientific interest (button 4 in Fig. 2) was made with a “force directed” map of an overall scientific journals list (Fig. 1), which used the spatial location of 45 basic disciplines. The areas of discipline nodes have colours appropriate to a given discipline, the boundaries between them have been marked conventionally (the layout in Fig. 3 is a mirror image and a rotated version of the discipline map from Fig. 1). On such a disciplinary map, each researcher can analyse the disciplinary profile of his/her publications and in which or close to which disciplinary area they are concentrated. The construction of such a map for a chosen scientist is presented in the section below. Using generated topology, the authors defined the parameter Multidisciplinary Area of Scientific Interests (MASI).

MASI

The concept of calculating the multidisciplinary coefficient assumes that if the force directed maps present in a general space of (post-classified) scientific knowledge, then each point in this space determines its relationship to the nearest disciplines. Articles are positioned at the centre of the geometric figure formed by the disciplines assigned to the journal. The equivalence of discipline nodes (no weights) explains this topology. The larger the area outlined by the article points, the larger the area of scientific interest. Thus, the area of polygons formed by the outermost nodes of the articles can be determined. In order to standardise area values, a reference parameter was introduced, i.e., the area of all disciplines on the map formed by the outermost nodes.

The MASI parameter is defined as a relation S_{art}/S_{disc} , where $S_{art} = \oint_{Pol} \Gamma(x_{ij})$ is the area of the polygon constructed on a disciplinary plan area and S_{disc} is an area created by the outermost discipline nodes (Fig. 3).

To estimate the coverage area “MASI”, we must first determine the location of the edge nodes for each discipline. The computational algorithm carries out this process by calculating the distances from the density centre of each research paper published in a journal assigned to a given discipline(s). This allows us to determine the location of nodes in the two-dimensional topological space (x_v, y_v) illustrated in Fig. 3.

Then the topological centre of a reconstructed map will be defined as:

$$\begin{cases} x_v = \frac{\oint x dS}{S} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i S_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n S_i} \\ y_v = \frac{\oint y dS}{S} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i S_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n S_i} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The theoretical value of the area integral is calculated iteratively as the sum of the products of the position coordinate (x_i, y_i) of the individual values of the area assigned to the specific visualized value. Determining the MASI parameter requires the use of the appropriately adjusted Monte-Carlo algorithm (Zhou & Cui, 2013) to calculate the area S_{art} within the polygon. Thus, we can use the standard algorithm based on image segmentation (Peng, Zhang & Zhang, 2011). To calculate the coverage region between two neighbouring regions R1 and R2 as the minimum weight edge, we should apply the following formula:

$$S(R_1, R_2) = \min_{v_i \in R_1, v_j \in R_2, (v_i, v_j) \in E} w((v_i, v_j)) \quad (2)$$

where (v_i, v_j) relates to each node on visual representation.

Parametrisation of the distance between the specific nodes makes it possible to estimate the value of the distance module, which normalizes the value of the surface integral needed to calculate the value of S_{art} .

MASI evaluation – a meso approach

The defined measure of multidisciplinary had to be tested on a real data set. The question then arose as to what values the MASI parameter takes, especially for scientists with a large scientific output, early-stage researchers such as PhD students, and the determination of the range of their values. The Expertus bibliographic database was again employed to collect data manually, this time using rankings automatically generated by the system. The university currently employs 1607 researchers. It was decided to integrate the Expertus data, and the data calculated in the SV application for those with the best scientometric parameters. The Expertus database was sorted in descending order, according to ministerial scores within each department, and then the top 30 records from each department were downloaded. The result was a set of 407 names, for which MASI data was generated in the SV application. Accordingly, the research sample was 25 % of the NCU academic staff and was representative of each organisational unit. The distribution of the MASI coefficient assumes a near exponential character (Fig. 4).

Figure 3. The map of disciplines as a space for representation of researcher's articles. The colours represent 8 domains, coloured circles – 46 disciplines ascribed to their domain, dark small points – researchers' articles forming the space of disciplines (green polygon). The outlined area is used as a reference for the calculation of MASI – equals 0.11 for the presented researcher.

The range of MASI values from 0.19 to a maximum of 0.32 falls into 15 names (Table 2). It can be noted that the MASI value in this range characterises physicists, astronomers, economists, political scientists, linguists (humanities) and those employed by the Centre for Modern Interdisciplinary Technologies, which has been in operation for 10 years (CMIT).

Figure 4. MASI factor distribution for the best NCU scientists on a linear and a log-log scale.

The fact that CMIT staff are associated with a wide range of disciplines should not be surprising. On the other hand, it was certainly a surprise that representatives of the social sciences and humanities, on a par with physicists and astronomers, are also in this field. Undoubtedly, further verification of the calculated values of the coefficients against a different database is necessary. Since 2022, the university has been transferring bibliographic data from Expertus to the Omega knowledge base available at: <https://omega.umk.pl/index.seam>. The Omega PSIR system, already implemented at 40 universities in Poland (*Omega-Psir*, 2020), was developed in 2012 by a team from the Warsaw University of Technology as part of the Synat technical project. The aim of this project (<https://www.cyfronet.pl/en>) was the creation of a universal, open repository hosting and communication platform for network knowledge resources for science, education and an open knowledge society. As each Open Science project, Omega enables indexing, sharing publications and other scientific achievements of the institution and its employees. It has a built-in repository of full-text and research data. It provides the ability to determine the license under which texts and research data were created, and to specify the level of availability or temporary suspension of availability (grace period). Thanks to synergy with the employee evaluation and appraisal module, it enables the effective creation of openness policies. The Omega platform makes articles and learning resources available for both editors and users and also activates a large community to share own solutions. Users will appreciate Omega's advantages over Expertus, such as a user-friendly interface equipped with visualisations, multi-faceted filters and greater functionality. Information scientists, on the other hand, will see a loss of important data, such as disciplines assigned to journals. In contrast, in Omega, information on collaborations has been expanded, using the researchers' declaration regarding the choice of one or two disciplines in which they publish.

The cooperation graph, therefore, contains information not only on the names, but also on the disciplines assigned to the names (Fig. 5). The working database was, therefore, extended to include data from disciplines and fields (colour-coded).

Fig. 5 presents the collaboration graph of selected computer scientists. It covers specialists from 5 disciplines: automation, electronic and electrical engineering, information and communication technology, psychology, communication and media studies, and veterinary science. However, the space of domain areas is reduced to 4: social science, natural science, engineering and agricultural science. These data are provided in the last two columns of Table 2, the appropriate row contains the numbers 5 and 4, respectively.

Pearson's correlation test was used to check the coherence of data in both columns (MASI and disciplines number in Table 2) referring to disciplinary characteristics in relation to each scientist. These dependencies are presented in Table 2.

By cutting-off the long tail of distribution, from 0.3%, we obtain a satisfactory statistically significant correlation of data from different databases describing different dimensions of multidisciplinary: publishing and social.

Discussion

The micro analyses of researcher's interests provided by the presented application use, as a referential base, the map of all scientific journals, indexed by the Polish Ministry of Science. In mapping, different layouts were tested, but, finally, a force-directed algorithm won due to qualitative-quantitative evaluation. During comparison, clustering quality, whereby local diversity as well as the neighborhood of groups - disciplines were included in domains, was taken into account (Osinska, 2020). Assuming that all Polish researchers choose the disciplinary-described journals from the above list for publishing, then they may find their own multidisciplinary representation on that map. The representation area in relation to the space surrounded by disciplines is used for the MASI calculation of an individual researcher.

Table 2. The first 15 scientists with the highest MASI coefficient.

<i>Rank</i>	<i>Researcher id</i>	<i>Faculty/Unit</i>	<i>MASI</i>	<i>Discipline number</i>	<i>Domain number</i>
1	R1	Centre for Modern Interdisciplinary Technologies	0.32	10	5
2	R2	Faculty of Political Science and Security Studies	0.29	4	1
3	R3	Faculty of Economic Sciences and Management	0.28	4	1
4	R4	Faculty of Economic Sciences and Management	0.27	3	1
5	R5	Faculty of Economic Sciences and Management	0.25	3	1
6	R6	Faculty of Economic Sciences and Management	0.25	2	1
7	R7	Centre for Modern Interdisciplinary Technologies	0.22	5	4
8	R8	Centre for Modern Interdisciplinary Technologies	0.22	4	1
9	R9	Faculty of Humanities	0.22	1	1
10	R10	Faculty of Humanities	0.22	3	1
11	R11	Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics	0.21	1	1

12	R12	Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics	0.21	4	1
13	R13	Faculty of Political Science and Security Studies	0.2	2	2
14	R14	Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics	0.19	2	1
15	R15	Faculty of Economic Sciences and Management	0.19	2	1

The way of description of MASI, where the outermost nodes of articles, which form the polygon area, causes that it has an increasing tendency. The location of any new article/journal node will extend the polygon area or not, but not decrease. Therefore, it is possible to investigate the dependence of MASI in relation to a researcher's career, albeit with a limitation of time range. Expertus is a source database making data about journal disciplines available since 2013. For instance, for a researcher, whose network is presented on Fig. 5, the MASI index has discretely changed from 0.04 (in 2013), 0.18 (2017) to 0.22 (2019 until now).

The MASI calculation method is suitable for academics with a wide range of research interests. Meso, i.e., university community level analyses of MASI variation shows that only the number of disciplines have an influence on its value. If a researcher starts to publish in a new discipline, the MASI discretely increases. For most scientists who are one- or two-discipline oriented, the (long tail) MASI should be redefined to sensitise the parameter to small correlation values. Further comparative studies of data from different academic centres are needed to establish appropriate cut-off ranges, which, in our analysis, were set at values of 30%, 45% and 75%. Arbitrary cut-offs may not be appropriate for other large research groups of scientists, as the leader group defining visible change may be above the 75% cut-off, depending on the size of the group and the number of discipline classes being analysed. The results of the analysis we obtained admittedly support the thesis put forward by Abramo, but only for the cut-off threshold used for the 75% value.

In the classification systems of Polish Science, created based on the Clarivate system, there are values defining domains (in Poland 8, WoS 3). The analysis proved that they are unhelpful in calculating the correlation coefficient of multidisciplinary studies. In this type of analysis, they can, therefore, be treated as artificial creations, which only find their rationale in one-domain studies.

Table 3. Results of correlation tests of the total set and after bottom cut-off.

<i>Dataset and bottom cutting in %</i>	<i>Pearson correlation</i>	<i>p</i>
Whole (0-1)	0.17	0,17
Cut-off (0-0.1)	0.24	0.16
Cut-off (0-0.3)	0.43	0.04
Cut-off (0-0.5)	0.58	0.04

A very important element in determining the coherence of the analysed issues of multidisciplinary of scientific collaboration in different research groups is the assumption that only those teams working in more than two disciplines should be analysed. When dealing with research carried out only in the area between two scientific disciplines, the values of correlation coefficients will always be dominated by the dominant discipline, and the research results do

not necessarily confirm this approach. Therefore, analysis using the MASI coefficient should only concern the analysis of those issues where research is carried out in more than just two domains.

Limitations

A common problem in the use of academic bibliographic databases is that they are incomplete and/or unevenly represented in relation to areas of knowledge (Engels, Ossenblok & Spruyt, 2009; Guns et al., 2018). In the given case, one could blame the lack of coherence of data in two databases, Expertus and Omega, although the latter was developed by transferring data from the former and then integrating it with data from the university's administrative database. In the given approach, disciplinary classification unfortunately does not include books, which are the main publishing medium for humanists and representatives of social sciences. The classification table only refers to journals on the ministerial list. However, it should be considered here that it is a tradition that humanists prefer to publish single-authored positions or positions with a small number of co-authors (Macfarlane et al., 2017; Verleysen & Ossenblok, 2017; Wang & Barabási, 2021).

Summary and conclusions

The article uses all scales of scientometric analysis. From macro measures aimed at creating an overall map of the journals in which a country's scientists publish and on the basis of which they are evaluated, to micro analyses, i.e., an individual view of the individual's own scientific achievements. The tool that makes this possible is the original Scientific Visualizer application. With it, researchers can analyse their scientific activity in different dimensions: temporal, geographical, disciplinary, and partnerships. To estimate the individual scope of research interests, the concept of calculating the MASI area in disciplinary space was presented.

By creating a university-level, or meso-level base, we analysed the behaviour of the proposed multidisciplinary factor within the community. It is easier to verify the obtained MASI values, especially the outliers, with an extended knowledge of careers of academic friends coming from the local community. For example, that physicists and chemists are keen to publish in international teams, astronomers conduct research only within astronomy, and psychologists and cognitive scientists often contribute to interdisciplinary research. Hence, the verification of individual records – the so-called micro approach – proved to be an important qualitative factor for scientometric analyses at the meso scale.

The multidisciplinary parameter has a distribution close to exponential. Only a small part of the academic community is characterised by high, above-average MASI values – for these values, the evaluation with correlation tests was positive. The proposal, while seemingly emblematic, should be complemented by additional empirical research to be scalable for other communities of researchers working in different countries and local settings. The use of the parametric evaluation system proposed in the paper should be implemented in analyses by other research teams. Only after the results for at least a few different academic centres have been obtained and verified should a comparative analysis be made, and general conclusions drawn.

Perhaps, the integration of the three levels of analyses will influence scientists to have more confidence in scientometric evaluation solutions that use not only traditional quantitative metrics, but also topological structures of maps of science. It is hoped that the approach presented, and the tools implemented will contribute to the researchers' consideration of multidisciplinary as a potential consideration in future research.

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